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SPECIFICITIES OF THE TEACHER TRAINING CARRIED OUT IN SOBRAL/CE AND THOSE SPECIFIC TO THE POA'S DUTIES IN THE RME-SP

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ABSTRACT

IN SME No. 25/2018 proposed the appointment of teachers to perform the role of Area Guidance Teacher (POA), intended for permanent teachers in the area of their assignment (SÃO PAULO, 2018b), to “monitor the planning of the actions of teachers in the areas/components of Literacy, Portuguese Language and Mathematics, together with the Pedagogical Coordinator, for the implementation of the City Curriculum of the respective areas/components.” (SÃO PAULO, 2018b). The citation, in a São Paulo institutional publication (SÃO PAULO, 2018e, p. 66), of the POA as a strategy inspired by the educational policy implemented in Sobral, required documentary research on the Ceará municipal initiative. In order to differentiate between the initiative carried out in Sobral/CE and the one instituted in the RME-SP, extensive documentary research was carried out on scientific articles and doctoral theses in the Google Scholar database, on the official portals of the respective city halls, on the DIEESE, OXFAM, IBEGE, IDEB portals and on the IPEA Portal. It was concluded that reflecting on planning in groups organized by area or by cycle enables teachers to individually and collectively revisit the contents of their educational experiences and practices, identify priorities, reframe knowledge and intervene in the construction of curricula together with other decisive agents in the process.

KEYWORDS: education; public education policy; teacher training; Sobral; São Paulo curriculum.

INTRODUCTION

In addition to updated guidelines on Learning Recovery activities, IN SME No. 25/2018 brought a new feature: the proposal to appoint teachers to perform the role of Area Guidance Teacher (POA).

A position intended for permanent teachers in their area of responsibility - Portuguese Language (Interdisciplinary and Authoring Cycles), Mathematics (Interdisciplinary and Authoring Cycles) or Teacher of Early Childhood Education and Elementary School I (PEIEF-I: Literacy Cycle) (SÃO PAULO, 2018b) -, the regulations required teachers to have:

[...] a minimum of 3 years of teaching experience in the São Paulo City Hall (PMSP); availability to attend the Educational Unit's Special Full Training Day (JEIF) groups; availability to participate in DIPED/SME training every two weeks and/or every month; and to monitor the planning of the actions of teachers in the areas/components of Literacy, Portuguese Language and Mathematics, together with the Pedagogical Coordinator, for the implementation of the City Curriculum in the respective areas/components. (SÃO PAULO, 2018b).

The citation, in a São Paulo institutional publication (SÃO PAULO, 2018e, p. 66), of the Area Guidance Teacher as a strategy inspired by the educational policy implemented in Sobral, required documentary research on the Ceará municipal initiative. In order to differentiate the relationships between the teacher training carried out in Sobral/CE and that for the exercise of the POA's attributions in the RME-SP, we carried out an extensive documentary search of scientific articles and doctoral theses in the Google Scholar database on the educational experience carried out in the municipality of Sobral.

Figure 4 - The municipality of Sobral/CE

Source: Adapted by the author (IBGE, 2017).

Figure 5 - The City of São Paulo/SP

Source: Adapted by the author (IBGE, 2017).

Figure 6 - The states of São Paulo and Ceará and their metropolitan regions

Source: Adapted by the author (IBGE, 2017)

Second in the ranking of the Human Development Index (HDI) in the state of Ceará, behind only the capital Fortaleza, Sobral has an estimated population of 210,711 people, an enrollment rate of 97.9% among students aged 6 to 14 and an IDEB of 9.1 in the Initial Years and 7.2 in the Final Years of the Public School System, according to IBGE data from 2017.

The educational public policy of the city of Sobral has attracted attention due to the evolution in

external evaluation indicators and the promotion of specific training for novice teachers, prompting academic studies on the process of implementing the public policy of continuing training in the municipality, which has resulted in professional improvement for teachers, above all for quality learning for students.

Adopting meritocracy and a policy of analyzing results as the parameters for awarding its teams of municipal education professionals, the school network has paid particular attention to continuing education, career plans, induction, welcoming and monitoring of new teachers. These awards were based on cross-checking information on the IDEB, Prova Brasil and HDI indicators, and are a constant feature of Sobral's experience.

DEVELOPMENT

Sobral was repeatedly awarded by the Anísio Teixeira National Institute for Educational Studies and Research (INEP) in 2005, whose Good Practices in Education project publicized the progress made in Sobral in the document *Overcoming the challenge of learning in the early grades: the experience of Sobral, covering the trajectory of educational policy from 1997 to 2004*.

In 2006, he won the Innovation in Educational Management award, entitled *Literacy Policy as a Strategy for Raising School Performance in the Early Grades of Elementary School*.

Sobral's experience also made up part of the report resulting from the partnership between UNICEF (United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund), MEC, INEP and UNDIME (National Union of Municipal Education Directors), entitled *Rede de aprendizagem - Boas práticas de municípios que garantem o direito de aprender*.

In 2008, the network's success was praised with the Innovation in Educational Management Award, with the publication *Strengthening School Management: selection by meritocratic criteria and continuing training for principals*.

In addition, two CENPEC Notebooks (Center for Studies and Research in Education, Culture and Community Action) collaborated with INEP publications in 2011, including the Literacy Program at the Right Age (PAIC) and, in 2012, the Lemann Foundation, in partnership with Itaú BBA, published the *Excellence with Equity* report. The Airton Senna Institute produced a video focusing on literacy and the OECD also praised the high levels of education achieved in Sobral in the Pisa, with the production of video documentaries, due to the jump from 4.0 in 2005 to 4.4 in 2009 in the IDEB score.

The non-negotiable agenda of attention to literacy teachers, ongoing training and rewards for successful results make up the tripod of the public policy of the education system in the city of Ceará, noting that basic teacher training was carried out in an outsourced partnership, constituting the successful Literacy Program at the Right Age (PAIC), which became a state and later federal program, called PNAIC. Between 2003 and 2006, the state government implemented Public Management by Results (*Gestão Pública por Resultados - GPR*), called *Ceará Cidadania, Crescimento com Inclusão Social* (Ceará Citizenship, Growth with Social Inclusion), with the aim of rationalizing investments of public resources, constituting yet another example of educational public policy employed through administrative and political programs in conjunction with measures to reform the public sector budget, fiscal adjustments and sanitation with a view to reducing the social abyss.

Drafted to support Ceará's state educational public policy, Law No. 15,923 of December 15, 2015 institutes the "Grade Ten School Award, designed to reward public schools with the best learning results in the second, fifth and ninth grades of elementary school" (CEARÁ, 2015).

In the very first article, the learning results, gathered through the School Performance Index (IDE), are determined as the parameters for awarding public schools and, from Article 2 onwards, there is a description of the criteria for awarding up to 150 schools in each category. With regard to literacy results, the award is

reserved for schools that can prove that they have more than 19 students enrolled in the second year of elementary school and a minimum of 90% of these evaluated with an average of more than 8.4 in the state of Ceará's own external evaluation system, the Permanent Evaluation System for Basic Education in Ceará (SPAECE), subject to tie-breaking criteria.

Similar to the criteria for the previous category, the 5th year of elementary school requires a minimum FDI average of 7.5 or above, as well as meeting the specific scales called "adequate", "very critical" and "critical" in the SPACE classification - specifications that determine the tie-breaking criteria stipulated. Below is a description of the award criteria for the 9th grade results, which are identical to the 5th grade criteria.

Article 5 stipulates that the value of the prize is R\$2,000.00 per student enrolled and assessed, deposited in a specific account in two installments (75% + 25%). Article 6 stipulates a financial contribution of R\$1,000.00 for each student enrolled and assessed in the 5th and/or 9th grades in two installments (50% + 50%) to the public schools with the lowest results, with the aim of implementing plans to improve student learning results, according to criteria which also stipulate that they can be awarded only once. Article 8 makes it compulsory for schools to enter into partnerships, either through awards or financial contributions:

Art. 8: Each of the schools awarded a prize as a result of the results obtained in the 5th and 9th grade assessments is obliged to develop, for a period of up to two (2) years, in partnership with one of the schools awarded a financial contribution, technical-pedagogical cooperation actions with the aim of maintaining or improving their students' learning results. (CEARÁ, 2015).

Article 9 warns that:

The transfer of the second installment of the financial contribution [...] is conditional on the achievement of targets for improving the results of underperforming schools, as determined annually by the Ceará State Department of Education (SEDUC). (CEARÁ, 2015).

Article 10 states that the funds received must be used exclusively for "actions aimed at improving learning outcomes" (CEARÁ, 2015) in accordance with SEDUC guidelines, and Article 11 prohibits the EU that has received an award or support from competing again in the subsequent year.

The formulas for calculating the SDI, guidelines, criteria and procedures for monitoring actions in relation to results will be the responsibility of a future Decree by the Head of the Executive Branch, as mentioned in Article 12, followed by the Article describing the specific arrangements for Pole Schools.

Article 14 stipulates that the transfer of financial resources must be in line with the Fiscal Responsibility Law (LRF); Article 15 guarantees that SEDUC will invest in the qualification of EUs that were not covered "involving the training of civil servants, improvements in physical and material structures, with a view to improving learning outcomes" (CEARÁ, 2015); followed by the effective date of this law, which repeals the previous one.

Led by the Sobral Municipal Department of Education (SEMED), the public policy implemented in the municipality has some characteristics (identified as determining factors) for the significant advances identified in the evolution of IDEB indicators.

In addition to the continuity of political-administrative management - which has allowed for consistency and consolidation of actions over time - various leaders from the territories' social collectives have risen to elected positions or have been nominated and appointed in various sectors at municipal, state and federal level, disseminating the GPR concept and providing cohesion for various public policies. Another important aspect is objective monitoring, with clear criteria, which has made accountability and symbolic or financial reward mechanisms possible. In other words, the secretariat emphasizes the relationship between teacher performance and improved student learning, due to the revision of normative acts and the curriculum, and the establishment of a bonus policy for teachers in relation to IDEB results.

SEMED relied on structure, resources and processes to ensure excellence in the development of actions, employing dynamics of demand and persuasion, which correspond to six intervention strategies: training professionals, evaluating students, improving databases, promoting the implementation of the project through the development and publication of specific subsidies and educational legislation.

In 1997 and 1998, training took the form of periodic lectures to teaching groups, given by SEMED employees. In 2001 there was a change in configuration, following a diagnostic assessment of the children's literacy levels, focusing training on reading and writing in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd years of elementary school and training on Saturdays, with bonuses for results in external assessments. In 2004, more systematic assessments and training were introduced and extended to kindergarten, 4th and 5th grades.

Ongoing training prioritized the management and training teams, bringing together principals and coordinators in all the EUs. The selection of members for these teams took place in 2001, by means of training for newcomers after a selection process among teachers with or without civil service exams, since there was no specific access via civil service exams. Of the 44 applicants, 20% were dismissed, with leadership and autonomy being essential characteristics. It should be noted that there was also a process of reframing the role of the school principal, as he or she had to reconcile work in the fields of administration, finance and pedagogy.

Thus, in proportion to the increase in demand for training, the need arose for a specialized team for the segments, outlining the dynamics of training and, in 2016, the School of Permanent Training for Teaching and Educational Management was founded (ESFAPEGE), a non-profit social organization under private law, constituting a space for valuing teaching professionals, aimed at promoting specific events for the exchange of successful experiences, cultural development and professional improvement. ESFAPEGE welcomed almost all of the trainers who were already experienced in this role, now enabling the teams

to become more cohesive and harmonious with each other in their conceptions and proposals, with the aim of improving the quality of student learning. There was also academic advice from the History and Social Memory of Education and Culture Research Group (GPHMSEC) at the Vale do Acaraú State University (UVA), which was very stimulating in terms of reflections and theoretical foundations.

The teachers' participation in actions to improve education began at the training meetings, bringing their experiences and conceptions in order to reflect on quality, learning and the re-signification of the teaching role. The training agenda dealt with communication, teaching skills and winning the interest of students, in other words, it brought to the center of the debate the quality of human relations, around which traditional content orbits. The training meetings were held monthly and the day's routine was agreed in groups, listing the schedule to meet the demands of the class, the timetable for the meetings, coordination meetings and the delivery of materials, and then the monthly activities were scheduled.

The leading role played by the organization of pedagogical practice in Sobral's public education policy permeated all dimensions, training, practices and projects, taking into account the re-signification of the qualification of teaching based on this pedagogical practice materialized in the teaching program (later called the curriculum proposal), in the classroom routine and in the structured material, a journey that was carried out in stages. The in-service training was aimed at all teachers, including beginners, in a non-school environment and covered all levels of education, in monthly meetings, focusing primarily on modifying pedagogical practices, interfering in the teaching routine and didactics in the classroom, with an emphasis on constant monitoring of the process of building students' learning.

The entire category was urged to work together to improve the learning results of students, a goal that can only be achieved through investment in the actions of school managers, in the organization of work, in a cooperative institutional climate, in the

appropriate use of available resources and in the participation of the local educational community. The co-responsibility of the grassroots not to naturalize precarious conditions and results was interpreted as promoting justice and social participation, providing spaces for dialogue, relevant procedures, clear objectives and realistic targets.

It was up to the RME-Sobral to provide specific support in terms of guaranteeing learning, focusing its efforts on solving everyday challenges and employing more appropriate strategies in the short and medium term, alongside collective, intense and disciplined work to train teachers in the process of seeking better results. The training of the team of trainers took place through study groups, reading books and taking part in educational academic events such as courses, congresses, seminars, symposiums and specializations.

Thus, the continuing education program focused on successful classroom practices, the search for excellence in teaching and knowledge of conceptual and procedural content. Therefore, the path to success, in the classroom, of the public educational policy implemented in the city of Sobral, Ceará, is summarized in four essential axes:

- Clear and achievable goals;
- Constant monitoring of student learning;
- Pedagogical actions based on learning data;
- A school environment conducive to the student's all-round development.

METHODOLOGY

There was a need to establish strict criteria for selecting the material, which corresponded to the fact that the published works were from 2016 - that is, contemporary to the initial period of construction of the São Paulo City Curriculum - and constituted master's dissertations or doctoral theses based on Law No. 15,923/2015 (CEARÁ, 2015). The references in these works provided essential sources for this research. At this stage of

writing the research, with the characterization of the experience of the RME of Sobral, it became possible to adjust the techniques of document collection and analysis, including editing and creating data spreadsheets and the most appropriate identification of recording units and categories for analysis.

The information on the Municipal Education Networks of the municipalities of São Paulo and Sobral, as well as statistical and demographic data, was collected through research carried out on the open databases of the respective municipalities (official portals) and on the DIEESE, OXFAM, IBEGE and IDEB portals.

Materials on the focus and procedures regarding initial and continuing teacher training specific to the RME-SP's POA public policy were found exclusively in the DIPED/DRE Penha digital public archive. The Open Data Portal provided access to the number of RME-SP enrollments and teachers. Gathering and organizing the data and processing the information in the spreadsheet editor was the strategy that preceded the preparation of the descriptive reports in the word processor, according to the perceptions derived from the simultaneous construction of the analysis diary. When necessary, statistical data was updated from the Knowledge Repository Portal of the Institute for Applied Economic Research (IPEA).

With a view to the quality of data collection on student learning, the subsidy for the periodic survey was published, and the document (cited in this research) points out the contribution of the POA in the process, stating that "this professional will be responsible for monitoring the planning of the literacy teachers' actions based on the survey data" (SÃO PAULO, 2019, p. 5).

In order to improve databases on the monitoring and improvement of learning and the results of internal and external assessments, SGP - a program whose screens replace the traditional paper Class Diary - was implemented in 2014 and has been improved with a view to optimizing the feeding, organization and access to information. There is no mention of specific strategies

to integrate families into this curricular implementation, and even the understanding and organization of the modality in cycles is not yet clearly addressed with families.

The OXFAM Brazil and Rede Nossa São Paulo: Mapa da desigualdade 2017 websites collected specific data on the Human Development Index for the metropolis of São Paulo, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - High and very high Social Vulnerability Index (SVI)

Source: Adapted by the author (RNSP, 2017, p. 23).

Offering 1,620 places, the SME-SP promoted initial and continuing training for POA professionals, amounting to 156 hours of training, the planning of which could be accessed and analyzed (DRE PENHA, 2020), with the information organized in Tables 9 and 10.

Chart 9 - RME-SP: POA formation process in the 1st and 2nd phases

GENERAL TRAINING OBJECTIVES

1. Understand the role of the POA in the school's training pathways;
2. Reflect on the organization of teacher planning in the light of the Curriculum, Teaching Guidelines and Cadernos da Cidade;
3. Discuss the constituent aspects of the Curriculum: Literacy Cycle, Portuguese Language and Mathematics;
4. To deepen theoretical aspects linked to the concept of literacy (in Portuguese and Mathematics) present in the City Curriculum.

Areas	Specific objectives	Training strategies
Literacy	1st phase: Identify the organizational modalities in a pedagogical routine for the Literacy Cycle; To analyze and understand the organization of the Activity Sequences in the Portuguese Language and Mathematics City Learning Books.	Process homology; Thematization of practice: analysis of teaching situations; Analysis of the Literacy Cycle City Notebooks;
	2nd phase: Strengthen the implementation of the city's curriculum; Study the SME documents - Literacy Cycle: Portuguese Language and Mathematics; Understand the concept of literacy in the City Curriculum.	Analysis of activity sequences; Case study.
Portuguese Language	1st phase: Immersion in the Portuguese Language City Curriculum; Reflecting on the object of knowledge: teaching; Reflecting on the teaching object: the text.	Double Conceptualization; Thematization of practice: analysis of teaching situations; Analysis of student productions: interaction and teacher intervention; Professional reading: deepening knowledge; Professional Writing: experiencing difficulties in writing.
	2nd phase: Poles Identity of the POA;	Sharing experiences; Reflect on teaching strategies;

Coordination with the Pedagogical Coordination.	Itineraries in the Educational Units (DRE).
1st phase: To study the theoretical and methodological assumptions of the Mathematics Curriculum in order to support the work of the Mathematics POA; To critically analyze POA practices in order to support the planning of didactic action in conjunction with the teachers of the component they are responsible for and with the Pedagogical Coordination.	Process homology; Thematization of practice: analysis of teaching situations.
2nd phase: Reflect on the different ways of organizing the classroom to enhance working with problem solving; Reflect on the Fundamental Ideas of Mathematics, through the notion of Equivalence and Proportionality; Deepen the study of the “Algebra” axis, focusing on the development of Algebraic thinking and the formal use of Algebraic language; Reflect on the strategies for monitoring learning in mathematics and relate them to	2nd phase: Poles Process homology; Thematization of practice: analysis of teaching situations; Case Study.

the importance of the teacher’s lesson plan, as well as the characteristics that need to be present in teaching practices in the classroom.	
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Source: Adapted by the author (DRE PENHA, 2020)

Chart 10 - Characterization of the identity of the POA function in the RME-SP

POA - Area Guidance Teacher	
Literacy/Portuguese Language/ Mathematics	
WHAT THE POA IS:	WHICH THE POA IS NOT:
Teacher who: She works in the EU, knows the PPP, the characteristics of the area and the City Curriculum, and deepens her studies by sharing practices; He works in partnership with his peers and CP, analyzing the results and planning proposals for interventions; Participates in collective moments to promote discussions and contribute ideas built up during the training course; Encourages the use of the network’s curriculum documentation.	Assisting CP in dividing up his duties; Professionals who intervene directly in the work of their colleagues; Exclusively responsible for ongoing training in collective hours and pedagogical meetings; Responsible for the actions of the PAP or Learning Recovery Project; Inspection of the use of curricular materials.

Source: Adapted by the author (DRE PENHA, 2020)

As for the RME-Sobral, in the Electronic Database of Thematic Laws of the Legislative Assembly of Ceará, we found Law No. 15.923/2015, which establishes the Grade Ten School Award, aimed at rewarding public schools with the best learning results in the second, fifth and ninth

grades of elementary school, which is included in Annex H of this work. By considering it, we can identify the legal basis for the dynamics of teacher training in the public educational policy instituted in the municipality of Ceará. Charts 11 and 12 summarize this process of initial and ongoing in-service teacher training, developed in stages.

	Series	Areas	Description
To the early grades	1st year	Morning: Portuguese Language	24 hours after the end of the meeting, the trainer in charge issues a report which is sent to ESFAPEGE and the school's pedagogical coordinator. The trainers/coordinators and presenters of the agendas are defined on a rota basis. The trainer/reporter is elected by the group or decided by drawing lots (CALIL, 2014).
		Afternoon: Mathematics, Science and Caring for the Teacher - Program focused on training teachers in the importance of vocal health care)	
	Other series	More time is allocated to Mathematics and Science and less to Portuguese Language, while maintaining Cuidando do Mestre	
To the final grades	From 6th to 9th grade (implemented in 2012)	Portuguese and English language training meetings: 4-hour meetings per month	Training meetings held by a mentor teacher, who will experience the training and pass it on to peers in the same area - a practice that inspired the POA public policy in the RME-SP.
		Training meetings for other areas: 2 hours per month.	

Chart 11 - Dynamics of in-service training at RME-Sobral

Source: Prepared by the author (2021).

Stage	Focus of attention	Study dynamics
1 ^a	That each teacher appropriates knowledge about the network and the contents of the grade, guided by the PCN, the	Meetings that brought together teachers by grade, starting the construction of the Curriculum Proposal,

	<p>reality of the territory and the demands of the school community.</p> <p>Promoting content knowledge aligned with pedagogical knowledge, through discussions between trainers and teachers in training courses.</p> <p>Preparation of the curriculum proposal, material and complementary activities.</p> <p>Deepening knowledge about conceptions, objects of knowledge, intentionality and teaching strategies.</p> <p>Analysis of didactic time, understanding this as the carrying out of reading, writing and production activities in a systematized way.</p>	<p>determining the minimum content for each grade.</p> <p>Preparation of structured material to work on the proposal.</p> <p>Study of real activities, to reflect on intentionality, objects of knowledge and meaningful learning.</p>
2 ^a	<p>Analysis of learning through successive organizations and reorganizations of knowledge, in a spiral.</p> <p>Using didactic time efficiently for the learning process requires an understanding that learning is not a linear process, requiring an equal change in the conception of the proposed activities.</p>	<p>The trainers visit the classroom to observe the proposed practices, collect information and discuss with the ESFAPEGE coordinators the relevant studies to be carried out in the teaching groups.</p>
3 ^a	<p>The quality of teaching and the optimization of teaching time depend on the teaching competence of the teacher.</p> <p>Promoting ongoing training that encourages permanent self-evaluation, a coherent professional base, aware of practice, motivated and engaged, acting with autonomy and excellence.</p>	<p>Preparing the classroom routine in line with the proposal and material, i.e. making sure that practice leads to achieving the objectives listed in the curriculum proposal.</p> <p>Establishing a routine for reflecting on the intentionality and quality of interventions in the light of learning objectives, so that the entire teaching team can use scientific, didactic and pedagogical knowledge to do so, paying attention to purpose, conditions and resources.</p>

Chart 12 - Stages in the development of in-service training in the RME-Sobral

Source: Prepared by the author (2021).

CONCLUSION

Following the example of the experience built up in the RME of the city of Sobral/CE, in the RME of the city of São Paulo, subsidies were produced with didactic guidelines and attention to the elaboration of the classroom routine and management, returning planning to the center of teacher training.

However, in addition to the huge data that characterizes the RME-SP, unlike what happened in Sobral, there was a change in the occupants of elected and appointed positions. The mayor elected in 2016, João Doria, administered the city from 2017 until April 6, 2018 (to take up the elective office of Governor of the State of São Paulo), and was succeeded by his vice-mayor Bruno Covas Lopes (who died on May 16, 2021). The main articulator of the POA public policy, Alexandre Schneider, appointed Secretary of Education in 2017, left his post in 2019 and, on January 8, 2019, the then mayor of São Paulo announced João Cury Neto as Municipal Secretary of Education. He was dismissed on July 4 of the same year and replaced by Bruno Caetano until January 2021, when Fernando Padula Novaes took over.

A key action for the POA's work, the organization of teacher training (both outside and in the Educational Unit itself) addressed reflection on teaching practices, monitoring the learning process through accurate records, attention to IDEB indices and the search for results.

Figure 12 - IDEB evolution: early grades

Source: Adapted by the author (QEDU, 2017c, 2017e)

Source: Adapted by the author (QEDU, 2017b, 2017f)

During the training, objective monitoring with clear criteria and the follow-up of IDEB results were discussed. There were no symbolic or financial reward mechanisms, but rather remuneration for the extra hours of teaching time set aside for compulsory training in the SME, DRE and UE, according to specific legislation commonly used in the São Paulo network.

W & S Assessoria e Consultoria LTDA - EPP was hired by the São Paulo City Council (PMSP) to advise on the construction of the new curriculum proposal for the city, and so the teaching teams contributed to the construction of the city's curriculum under the guidance of Professor Telma Weisz.

Along with Emilia Ferreiro and Ana Teberosky, Telma Weisz is one of a group of educators who have influenced the training of Brazilian public school teachers, especially in the São Paulo state school system. She has a PhD in Learning and Development Psychology from the Institute of Psychology at the University of São Paulo. She took part in the drafting of the National Curriculum Parameters (PCN), created and supervised the Literacy Teacher Training Program (PROFA) at the MEC, which in the state of São Paulo was called Letra e Vida (Letter and Life). She has been the coordinator and teacher of the Classroom Practice Thematization Group since 2003. From that year to 2013, she prepared the 1st to 3rd year Portuguese language tests for SARESP and supervised the Ler e Escrever Program at the São Paulo State Department of Education from 2007 to 2014. She has been coordinator and teacher of the Specialization Course in Literacy at the Vera Cruz Higher Institute of Education in São Paulo since 2005, and teacher-researcher at

the Specialization and Master's Degree in Writing and Literacy at the Faculty of Humanities and Educational Sciences of the National University of La Plata since 2007. In 2017, she took part in the preparation of the São Paulo City Curriculum and Teaching Guidelines in the area of Elementary School Portuguese Language.

A consultant in educational projects with a constructivist profile, Telma Weisz has been pushing public schools, more specifically in São Paulo, to bring up issues that are dear to their hearts and everyday classroom reality: what students already know from their experiences, the importance of planning and teacher training. After completing this stage and the curricular aids, it was up to the SME-SP team of trainers to promote ongoing teacher training in a network, to encourage the implementation of the project and the construction of the identity of the POA function, through the preparation and publication of specific aids and educational legislation.

SME-SP promoted initial and continuing training for POA professionals, which amounted to 156 hours of training offered to 1,620 vacancies. The initial training (outlined in Ordinances No. 3,791, No. 3,792 and No. 3,793 of April 17, 2019) allocated 100 places to the POA - Mathematics, 100 places to the POA - Portuguese Language and 200 places to the POA - Literacy, as determined by Communiqué No. 295, Communiqué No. 314 and Communiqué No. 313, published in the DO.online on April 11, 2017. The training meetings for the first semester of 2019 began at the end of April and were held in central locations in the city, which were lent free of charge. The meetings in the second semester took place in the Regional Education Directorates (in the case of the Literacy and Portuguese Language POA) and in hubs (teachers from two or more DREs meeting in the same place) for the Mathematics POA.

This research concluded that reflecting on planning in groups organized by area or by cycle is a promising trend, as it allows teachers to individually and collectively revisit the contents of their educational experiences and practices, identify priorities, resignify knowledge and

intervene in the construction of curricula together with other decisive agents in the process. Arroyo (2007) emphasizes that the reflective practice carried out in teaching collectives provides the production of other diverse pedagogical knowledge and resources, making these educators collective producers of the curriculum and, therefore, co-responsible for it. "Mapping and exchanging" these collective practices is an exercise proposed by Arroyo (2007, p. 20).

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